

Open Access session 1

By Rania Baleela

Was composed of the 4 following parts:

1. Introduction to Open Access:

Presentation attached.

2. FAIR data principles:

These are a measurable set of principles used to improve the infrastructure supporting the reuse of scholarly data.

First mentioned in:

The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship:

<https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

3. Persistent identifiers (PIDs):

- ORCID: <https://orcid.org/>
- The Research Organization Registry (ROR): <https://ror.org/>
- Digital Object Identifier (DOI): <https://www.doi.org/>
- FREYA the power of PIDs (Watch the video): <https://youtu.be/fwlePgYar58?si=iPC9HYK4mxjwNdzp>

4. Principles for Open Access in Scholarly Communication in and about Africa:

10 principles Developed by AfricArXiv:

1. Academic Research and knowledge from and about Africa should be freely available to all who wish to access, use or reuse it while at the same time being protected from misuse and misappropriation.

2. African scientists and scientists working on African topics and/or territory will make their research achievements including underlying datasets available in a digital Open Access repository or journal and an explicit Open Access license is applied.
3. African research output should be made available in the principle common language of the global science community as well as in one or more local African languages.
4. It is important to take into consideration in the discussions indigenous and traditional knowledge in its various forms.
5. It is necessary to respect the diverse dynamics of knowledge generation and circulation by discipline and geographical area.
6. It is necessary to recognize, respect and acknowledge the regional diversity of African scientific journals, institutional repositories and academic systems.
7. African Open Access policies and initiatives promote Open Scholarship, Open Source and Open Standards for interoperability purposes.
8. Multi-stakeholder mechanisms for collaboration and cooperation should be established to ensure equal participation across the African continent.
9. Economic investment in Open Access is consistent with its benefit to societies on the African continent – therefore institutions and governments in Africa provide the enabling environment, infrastructure and capacity building required to support Open Access.
10. African Open Access stakeholders and actors keep up close dialogues with representatives from all world regions, namely Europe, the Americas, Asia, and Oceania.

Summary of the Principles for Open Access in Scholarly Communication in and about Africa in addition to CARE principles:

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Open Access

About me

Rania Mohamed Hassan Baleela

Sudanese Molecular Biologist

Openness Trainer

U. of K. & LSHTM Alumni

EFL.net OA Sudan coordinator (2012–April 2024)

RSTMH Sudan Ambassador (2020–present).

Definitions & history

Open Science (FOSTER definition):

Open Science is the practice of science in such a way that others can collaborate and contribute, where research data, lab notes and other research processes are freely available, under terms that enable reuse, redistribution and reproduction of the research and its underlying data and methods.

In simpler terms?

**Free access to
information**

**Unrestricted use
of resources for
everyone**

**Texts , data,
software, audio,
video, etc.**

A publication is considered in OA if:

Freely accessible

No cost to the reader

Via the Internet or otherwise

The right to use

Proper attribution

Deposited in an OA repository

OA

**contributions
must satisfy:**

TWO CONDITIONS

1. Free, irrevocable,
worldwide, right of
access

2. Deposited in an
online repository

Historical milestones

Berlin Declaration

 openaccess.mpg.de

The Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities was published on 22 October 2003 in English.

“Our mission of disseminating knowledge is only half complete if the information is not made widely and readily available to society.”

Read the Declaration

Budapest Open Access Initiative An old tradition and a new technology have converged to make possible an unprecedented public good. The old tradition is the willingness of scientists and schola

 [Budapest Open Access Initiative /](#)

Strategies

Self-Archiving

Strategies

2. Open-access Journals

On average, open access journal articles are cited

45% –
more often 600%

than closed access articles,
depending on the scientific discipline

Routes

Golden

Full OA journals

Green

Hybrid Journals

Diamond

Article Processing Charges (APCs)

A one-off payment to cover the costs of publishing and publishing services in gold or hybrid Open Access journals.

Paying this fee means that your research will be open immediately upon publication with a Creative Commons license via the publisher's website.

APC fees vary by journal.

Diamond OA journals/ platforms

- no APC
- Free to access/read
- Free to publish in.

These initiatives are usually non-profit, run by and for academics.

Plan S

Golden route

Plan S

Making full and
immediate
Open Access a
reality

Why OA?

Boost the visibility,
dissemination, use &
impact of your work

Deposit

A copy of your
work in a repository

What can you do?

Be aware of your rights
use of Creative Commons
licenses to organise your rights
CC BY

The future of science is Open